

A preliminary design of a high-fidelity vessel anastomosis simulator

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Abstract— A high-fidelity simulator for surgical vessel anastomosis was designed and a first prototype was here realised by using a silicone vessel with an integrated mesh that allows to avoid any damages due to the needle passage during suturing. A preliminary system assessment was performed, but future efforts are required for a complete validation process.

Keywords—high-fidelity simulation, anastomosis leakages, soft materials

I. INTRODUCTION AND STATE OF THE ART

Anastomosis is the medical term used for indicating a surgical connection between two tubular structures or channels that typically do not attach. In surgery, an anastomosis occurs when a clinician connects two structures in the body. Focusing on *vascular anastomosis*, it is the clinical term for connecting/reconnecting vessels to each other to restore normal blood flow to the affected area.

The most serious complication of the procedure is the anastomotic leak (AL), which can occur when the two ends of a channel don't seal completely, and contents from the inside leak out. Most leaks show up within the first week after surgery, but some may occur later, causing serious problems for the patient [1], e.g., about four weeks of hospital stays.

ALs are reported in about 5% of anastomosis surgeries ([link](#)). Despite about 75% of them are associated with colectomy (i.e., removal all or part of colon), the attention of the surgical community towards vascular anastomosis leaks is recently growing highlighting the importance of a valid training process. Vascular anastomosis training is a technically challenging issue and necessitates a long learning curve [2]. Simulation-based learning can thus provide necessary training and practice outside the operating room. Therefore, simulation models have to be designed to provide opportunities for practising vascular anastomosis prior to clinical applications by residents or surgeons.

Simple vascular anastomosis kit simulators are available on the market, e.g., the SimuVasc Trainer that consists of a portable model to perform all the steps of a vascular anastomosis ([simuvasc](#)). The system is designed to be a low-fidelity vessel replica for the acquisition of basic vascular surgery skills. On the contrary, to the best of our knowledge, few physical simulators allowing the suturing procedure have been found in the literature. A 3D printing for anastomosis between an artery and a vein is reported in [3]. Taking advantage of the 3D printing process, high fidelity vessel

simulators are guaranteed. However, the absence of technical components for simulating the blood flow and the used materials that are very far from human blood vessels, highlight significant limitations of the proposed system. Some of these drawbacks have been solved in the simulator proposed in [4] for the suturing of the femoral-popliteal artery. The main improvement introduced by this model was the use of a pump to simulate blood flow. However, the system appears cumbersome and quite rigid and the selected material was not properly similar to a real artery [4].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The aim of this paper is designing a high-fidelity vascular simulator for training surgical anastomosis task equipped with a control mechanism for ALs evaluation. The main anatomical components of the simulator are the vessel and the actuation system for replicating the human blood circulation. The vascular structure is simulated as a soft cylindrical tube whose dimensions were tuned with respect to the anatomical one [5]. Thus, the dimensions reported in literature and replicated in the design of the vascular structure are the following: length of 100 mm, diameter of 8 mm and wall thickness of 1 mm [5]. A support structure was also designed and realized to improve the simulator usability and portability and especially for housing a pump used for circulating liquids in the vessel and thus evaluate the leaks. More specifically, a reservoir was designed on the upper part of the support structure to collect and calculate the liquid, i.e., the simulated blood, lost during the anastomosis procedure. It is immediately under the vessel housing properly equipped with two anchoring systems used to easily lock the vessel at the support structure and make the simulator “plug and play”. To realize the anatomical components of the simulator, moulds have been designed with Fusion 360 software (Autodesk, CA, USA) and 3D printed in polylactic acid with an Original Prusa i3 MK3s+ 3D printer (Prusa Research, Czech Republic). Silicone Ecoflex 00-30 (Smooth-On, USA) was used for the vein simulator casting, providing a good compromise in terms of flexibility, softness and structural integrity, moreover it is recognized in literature to have mechanical properties like human soft tissues and muscle [6]. However, by passing a surgical needle through the silicone vessel for simulating the suturing task, Ecoflex was significantly damaged. For solving this drawback, commercial meshes were incorporated on the silicone structure during the moulding process (Fig.1(A)).

The mesh that better replicate the biomechanical properties of the human vein was selected through a tensile tests performed at the Instron machine (Instron, USA). Three different commercial meshes (white, yellow and brown meshes – Fig.1(B)), with different properties, have been included in the silicone samples and the force-displacement curves were acquired and compared with porcine vein and artery data, being porcine tissues very similar to the adult human one. A monoaxial tensile test was performed by using an elongation range from the 0% to the 50% with a rate of 150 mm/min. The rate was arbitrarily chosen not having clinical and literature references to use. The decision of doing the tests from 0% to 50% of the vessel elongation derives from the need to compare the obtained curves with the literature data about Ecoflex 00-30, porcine vein and artery.

Fig. 1 (A) Fabrication process. (B) Types of meshes tested. (C) Final prototype of the simulator for anastomosis procedure.

III. RESULTS

The final prototype of the vascular anastomosis simulator is presented in Fig.1(C). Based on the tensile test data (Fig. 2), the vein simulator was realised embedding into silicone synthetic fibres of the brown mesh that better replicate the features of the porcine vessels - white and yellow meshes are too stiff if compared with porcine curves. However, the curve obtained with the brown mesh is more similar to the porcine artery (mean error equal to 0.0052 ± 0.0033 MPa) instead of the porcine vein. Thus, for a vein simulator, the selected sample is too rigid. Additional investigations on the available meshes have been then carried out; first, cyclic monoaxial tensile tests with 3 up and down cycles were performed to better understand the complete behaviour of the silicone-brown mesh sample. Moreover, for evaluating the damages limit of the sample, it was stretched up to the 200% of strain. From the obtained curves (data not reported for space limitations) mesh damages are observed after the 150% of strain. Considering that, an additional tensile test was performed by using “the-brown-mesh-after-the-break” sample and the stress-strain curve was totally different from the previous one (Fig.2). Sample is now less rigid than the previous one, and it is now moved towards the porcine vein curve (mean error about 0.0091 ± 0.0030 MPa). A preliminary validation by involving a robotic surgeon was carried out (Fig.3). An anastomosis procedure was simulated by evaluating both the leakages and the timing for accomplishing

the entire task. The system was robust and the simulation was performed without any major problems. The surgeon was positively surprised about the fidelity of the system, both in terms of tactile feedback and tissue reaction to the needle puncturing. Additional investigations are anyway required for the assessment of the proposed system and thus for a complete validation session.

Fig. 2 Stress-strain curves comparison between silicone, different meshes and porcine vein and artery data.

Fig. 3 - Frame from the surgeon validation task.

IV. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

A high-fidelity simulator for surgical vessel anastomosis training was designed, a first prototype realised and preliminary validated. However, different system could be envisaged by varying the vessel parameters; different vessel diameter or wall thickness require specific suturing force. I.e., from 0 to 10% of strain, the obtained curves are similar, so all the three proposed meshes – or the simple silicone sample – could be used for simulating the porcine behaviour. On the contrary, for higher strain percentage the meshes behaviour changes and a selection is required based on the simulator applications where simplicity, robustness or high/low-fidelity could affect the designing choices.

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